

PROCESSING OF HIGH-TEMPERATURE SUPERCONDUCTING COMPOSITES FOR BULK APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The inherently weak mechanical properties of monolithic high-temperature superconductors (HTS) can be improved by introducing properly selected strong ceramic fibers or whiskers into the HTS ceramics. In this research, processing studies of continuous Al_2O_3 -fiber and MgO-whisker reinforced BPSCCO HTS composites are presented. Processing methods for both the $(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_f/\text{BPSCCO}$ and $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$ composites are introduced. The composites are shown to exhibit a combination of desirable superconducting and mechanical properties. Important relationships among processing variables, microstructure, and properties of the HTS composites are established. Also, critical issues on the composite microstructure and the microchemistry at the fiber (or whisker)/matrix interface are addressed.

INTRODUCTION

With recent discoveries of various high-temperature superconducting (HTS) materials [1,2,3,4], a large number of studies have been conducted to address their superconducting properties in bulk forms, such as the critical temperature (T_c) and the critical current density (J_c). In addition, small-scale superconducting prototypes have been successfully developed for studying their full commercial potentials. The bulk applications include superconducting energy storage systems [5], magnetic bearings [6], cryogenic current leads [7], fault current limiters [8] and others. In these applications, superconducting materials are employed in cryogenic environments where magnetic and electrical fields are present. Induced thermomechanical stresses, such as the Lorentz force and residual thermal stresses, as well as associated deformations in the bulk HTS materials are expected, due to strong coupling among the thermal, electrical, magnetic and mechanical fields. Thus, for bulk applications, in addition to retaining the desirable superconducting properties, the HTS materials need to be strengthened and toughened to sustain long-term static or cyclic thermomechanical loading.

In the literature, attempts have been made to improve mechanical properties of the HTS materials by introducing a small amount of second phase, such as metal particles [9], polymers [10] and oxides [11]. However, the improvement has been limited. The use of high-strength/high-modulus fibers or whiskers to strengthen and toughen the inherently weak and brittle ceramics has been a common practice for developing advanced structural ceramics. The introduction of strong ceramic whiskers or fibers into high-temperature superconducting materials to maintain desirable, combined thermomechanical and superconducting properties has only been considered recently [12,13]. In this paper, processing studies of continuous Al_2O_3 -fiber and MgO-whisker reinforced BPSCCO HTS composites are conducted, and critical results are shown.

SELECTION OF MATRIX AND REINFORCEMENT MATERIALS

In this study, a Pb-doped, Bi-2223 (BPSCCO) HTS material was considered as the matrix material. Reasons for this selection, as compared with the well-known YBCO-123, are: (1) relatively low solid-state processing temperature ($<850^{\circ}\text{C}$); (2) high critical transition temperature (about 110 K); (3) better chemical compatibility with ceramic reinforcements; and (4) a dense and textured microstructure achievable by solid-state processing.

Continuous Al_2O_3 fibers and MgO whiskers were selected as reinforcement materials, owing to thermodynamic, thermal and mechanical property compatibilities with the BPSCCO matrix at elevated processing and cryogenic service temperatures, which will be discussed in the following sections.

Thermodynamic & Thermal Property Compatibility

It is recognized that only very few materials are chemically compatible with the BPSCCO compound at a high processing temperature [11]. Silver may be the only known metal chemically compatible with the BPSCCO when processed in a low oxygen pressure atmosphere. Among various high-strength oxides, MgO and Al_2O_3 are fully and partially compatible with the BPSCCO [11], respectively. Therefore, commercially available Al_2O_3 fibers and MgO whiskers were selected in this study.

In addition, thermal properties are also important in the development and applications of the HTS composites. The effective thermal conductivity of an HTS ceramic may be improved by introducing a selected reinforcement thermally compatible with the HTS matrix. Residual thermal stresses in an HTS composite may be minimized if the thermal expansion mismatch between the two phases is minimal. The thermal conductivity and the thermal expansion coefficient of a polycrystalline BPSCCO HTS material at room temperature are about 1 W/mK and $11.7 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$ [14], respectively. Compared with the BPSCCO phase, MgO whiskers have a compatible thermal expansion coefficient ($12.8 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$) [15] and thermal conductivity (60W/mK) [16]. Minimal residual thermal stresses are expected in the $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite during cooling from an elevated processing temperature to a cryogenic service temperature. The Al_2O_3 fibers, however, have a lower thermal expansion coefficient ($5.5 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$) [17] and a higher thermal conductivity (40 W/mK) [16] than those of the BPSCCO. The compatible thermal properties between the reinforcement and the matrix are important in realizing both superconducting and mechanical properties of the HTS composites.

Mechanical Properties of Reinforcement and Matrix Materials

Both Al_2O_3 fibers and MgO whiskers possess superior mechanical properties. Their Young's moduli and tensile strengths are reported to be 380 GPa and $>1,400$ MPa for the Al_2O_3 fibers [18], and 250GPa and $>1,000$ MPa for the MgO whiskers [19], respectively. These values are far better than those of the monolithic BPSCCO HTS material, which are reported to be 150-216 GPa and 174 MPa [20]. Introduction of Al_2O_3 fibers and MgO whiskers into the BPSCCO matrix is expected to provide a composite with desirable combined mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Processing of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ HTS Composite

As illustrated in Fig. 1, an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite was fabricated initially by a slurry method, followed by binder extraction up to 800°C in an 8% O_2 atmosphere, and finally hot pressed at 800°C in air. The smooth slurry was prepared by mixing proper amounts of the BPSCCO powder and organic binders. Alternating layers of the prepared BPSCCO slurry and aligned Al_2O_3 fiber yarns were subsequently laid in an aluminum template, followed by drying in a vacuum desiccator. Extensive caution has to be taken during the binder extraction step. The binders were removed very slowly to prevent any rapid decomposition. Rapid reactions were observed to cause

detrimental delaminations in the composite, or uncontrollable matrix reactions which might completely destroy the original Bi-2223 phase. Optimum binder extraction was achieved by an incremental heating process up to 800°C in an 8% oxygen atmosphere, with several short isothermal steps at selected temperatures (Fig. 1). After the binder extraction, the Al₂O₃/BPSCCO composite was hot pressed at 800°C in air at a selected pressure from 2.8 to 7.6 MPa.

Fig. 1 Fabrication process of Al₂O₃-fiber reinforced BPSCCO composite.

Processing of (MgO)_w/BPSCCO HTS Composites

Processing a (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite was more straightforward, when compared with the Al₂O₃/BPSCCO processing, using a solid-state processing method. The BPSCCO powder was first wet-mixed with a proper amount of MgO whiskers. The mixing was conducted in an isopropyl alcohol for a specific amount of time to achieve mixing uniformity of the BPSCCO powder with the MgO whiskers, meanwhile retaining reasonable aspect ratios of the MgO whiskers. The green composite specimens were first formed by dry pressing at the room temperature, followed by a hot pressing at elevated temperatures to achieve: (1) densification of the BPSCCO matrix and improvement of the intergrain connection in the HTS composite with plastic deformation at high temperatures; (2) aligning plate-like BPSCCO matrix grains in a hot-pressing plane to form a dense layered microstructure; and (3) aligning the MgO whiskers along the plane perpendicular to the hot-pressing direction. A proper repetition of hot pressing and annealing was found to be necessary for further densifying and texturing the microstructure of the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite. It was concluded by experiments that a three-cycle hot-pressing and annealing process, as shown in Fig. 2, with an increasing hot-pressing pressure, from 13.8 MPa to 34.5 MPa, gave an excellent J_c for the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite.

Fig. 2 Three-cycle hot-pressing and annealing process for (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Processing and Resulting Microstructure Al₂O₃/BPSCCO HTS Composite

Following the processing method described in the previous section, an Al₂O₃/BPSCCO composite was fabricated with a consistently good quality. The SEM micrograph shown in Fig. 3(a) reveals the typical microstructure of the composite. Alternate Al₂O₃ fiber-rich and BPSCCO matrix-rich

layers may be identified in the composite. As expected, the pressure applied during hot pressing caused plate-like BPSCCO-2223 grains in the matrix to align along preferred directions. As shown in Fig. 3(b), in regions away from the Al_2O_3 fibers, the Bi-2223 grains tended to align along the plane perpendicular to the hot-pressing direction, resulting in a densely stacked microstructure. Adjacent to the fiber/matrix interface, the 2223 grains were circumferentially oriented around the fibers.

Fig. 3 Micrographs of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite showing: (a) an overall composite microstructure, and (b) Al_2O_3 fibers and BPSCCO matrix grains.

Three pressure levels were selected to evaluate the effect on the HTS composite. A pressure higher than 7.6 MPa was not used because it might damage the Al_2O_3 fibers. The final fiber volume fraction in the hot-pressed specimens increased with the applied pressure, as expected, ranging from 0.12 (at 2.8 MPa) to 0.15 (at 7.6 MPa).

Superconducting Properties of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ Composite

The hot-pressed $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite was subjected to four-probe ac resistivity measurements. In Figs. 4(a) and 4(b), effects of the hot-pressing pressure and time are shown. For comparison, the resistivity obtained from a hot-pressed monolithic specimen is also included. The normal-state resistivity of the monolithic BPSCCO was smaller than those of the HTS composite. Since Al_2O_3 fibers were essentially electrically insulating, they were not expected to contribute to the effective composite electrical conductivity. Also observed in Fig. 4(a) are the superconducting transition temperatures, T_c , of the monolith and the composite specimens prepared under 5.6 MPa and 7.6 MPa pressure, both at about 100 K, while another composite specimen, hot pressed at 2.8 MPa, showed a lower T_c at about 90K. In the HTS composite, the transport current was expected to pass through the easiest path, i.e., the dominant Bi-2223 matrix phase. When the applied pressure was relatively low, as in the case of 2.8 MPa, the 2223 matrix grains did not have as a good intergrain contact as that obtained under a higher pressure. Nevertheless, increasing the applied pressure from 5.6 MPa to 7.6 MPa only slightly affected the resulting normal-state resistivity and T_c . The effect of hot-pressing time on the superconducting properties of the composite is shown in Fig. 4(b). A longer heat treatment apparently led to a better overall effective superconductivity, caused by a more favorable matrix microstructure, due to the enhanced 2223 matrix grain growth and reduction in grain boundary weak links.

Mechanical Properties of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ Composite

In Fig. 5(a), typical stress-strain relationships are shown for a $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite tested at 293 and 77 K, and a monolithic BPSCCO at 293 K. The failure strength of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite was significantly improved to about 85 MPa, as compared with that of the monolithic specimen (40 MPa). Unlike the linear σ - ϵ behavior of the monolithic BPSCCO, transitions were recorded in the stress-strain curves of the HTS composites. The successive linear regions with reduced stiffnesses suggest an increase in matrix microcracks, resulting from thermal stresses generated from processing and/or cooling, due to the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients of the Al_2O_3 fibers and the BPSCCO matrix.

Fracture toughnesses determined for both the monolithic BPSCCO and the HTS composite at 77K were shown in Fig. 5(b). As expected, the value of K_{Ic} was independent of the crack length. The fracture toughness of the Al_2O_3 /BPSCCO composite was noted to be dramatically increased at 77K. Toughening by the Al_2O_3 fibers is clearly demonstrated. Toughening mechanism, however, could be complex, due to multiphase constituents with different thermomechanical properties.

Fig. 4 Effects of (a) applied pressure, and (b) hot pressing time on normal-state resistivity and superconducting critical temperature of Al_2O_3 /BPSCCO composite. (Four-probe ac resistivity measurements.)

Fig. 5 Mechanical properties of monolithic BPSCCO and Al_2O_3 /BPSCCO composite: (a) stress-strain relationships at 293K and 77K, and (b) fracture toughnesses at 77K.

Processing and Microstructure of $(MgO)_w$ /BPSCCO HTS Composite

Owing to the aforementioned better chemical compatibility between the $(MgO)_w$ and the BPSCCO matrix, a higher hot-pressing temperature and longer heat-treatment time were selected for processing the $(MgO)_w$ /BPSCCO system to improve the microstructure and, consequently, resulting composite superconducting and mechanical properties. Hot pressing was recognized to density the BPSCCO matrix; and subsequent long-term annealing was for "healing" various kinds of microdamage induced during the hot pressing, improving the BPSCCO phase purity, and refining the matrix microstructure. In this study, it was also found that repeated cycles of hot pressing and annealing, with an increasing hot-pressing pressure up to 34.5 MPa, always led to a highly dense and layered matrix microstructure consisting of highly pure BPSCCO phase, as shown in Fig. 6(a). In Fig. 6(b), MgO whiskers in the hot-pressed $(MgO)_w$ /BPSCCO composite are shown to be nearly randomly oriented in the plane normal to the hot-pressing direction. After repeated hot pressing and annealing, the matrix density in the $(MgO)_w$ /BPSCCO could reach as high as 6.3 gm/cm³, which is about 97% theoretical density of the material.

Superconducting Properties of $(MgO)_w$ /BPSCCO Composite

As a non-conducting second phase in the superconducting BPSCCO matrix, MgO whiskers possessed excellent mechanical properties and chemical compatibility. However, the presence of

the MgO whiskers may cause limited decomposition of the BPSCCO phase during an initial hot pressing, due to high temperature and local stress concentrations. The decomposed BPSCCO phase was fully recovered during a subsequent long-term annealing in an 8% O₂ atmosphere. As indicated in Fig. 7, values of the T_c of the monolithic BPSCCO and (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite (with v_w=10% and v_w=20%), after three-cycle hot pressing and annealing, were almost the same. The MgO whiskers therefore did not have an appreciable effect on the high-T_c phase purity after a long-term heat treatment. The critical current density, J_c, however, was adversely affected by the presence of the MgO whiskers, especially in the composite with a high (MgO)_w volume fraction. In Fig. 8, the transport J_c were shown in a two-cycle (for the monolithic) and a three-cycle (for the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite) hot-pressing and annealing process. A significant amount of improvement in J_c was observed in each step of hot pressing and annealing, attributable to Bi-2223 phase enhancement and microstructure refinement.

Fig. 6 Typical microstructure of (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite; (a) in a cross-section parallel to the hot-pressing direction, showing well-aligned BPSCCO grains, and (b) in a cross-section normal to the hot-pressing direction, showing random orientation of MgO whiskers.

Fig. 7 Resistivity vs. temperature of monolithic BPSCCO and (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite with v_w=10% and v_w=20% after three-cycle hot pressing and annealing.

Fig. 8 J_c (77K and zero field) of monolithic BPSCCO and (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite with v_w=10% and v_w=20% in two-cycle and three-cycle hot pressing and annealing.

Mechanical Properties of (MgO)_w/BPSCCO Composite

The (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composites were subjected to tensile strength and fracture toughness tests at room temperature. In Fig. 9(a), relationships between the tensile strength and the whisker volume fraction (v_w) were shown. With an addition of 10% MgO whiskers, the tensile strength of the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite was improved from 108 MPa to above 120 MPa. In the HTS composite with $v_w=20\%$, however, the variation of the composite tensile strength became large. This may be attributed to a distorted microstructure of the BPSCCO matrix. The BPSCCO grain growth was substantially impeded by the high whisker volume fraction.

The fracture toughness of the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite was also observed to increase with the introduction of the MgO whiskers. As shown in Fig. 9(b), K_{Ic} of the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO increased from 2.6 to 3.2 (MPa.m^{1/2}) as the v_w increased from 0 to 20%. Toughening mechanisms observed in the (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite included whisker pull-out and crack deflection.

Fig. 9 Mechanical properties of monolithic BPSCCO and (MgO)_w/BPSCCO composite, showing the effect of (MgO)_w volume fraction on: (a) tensile strength, and (b) fracture toughness.

Microstructure and Microchemistry at Reinforcement/Matrix Interface

Since the Al₂O₃ fibers were partially compatible with the BPSCCO matrix during heat treatment (at 840°C for 24 hours), potential fiber/matrix interfacial reactions during the processing were expected and evaluated with a SEM and an EPMA. SEM observations of the HTS composites undergone different periods of hot pressing were performed. A distinct reaction layer of approximately 5 μm thick, as shown in Fig. 10(a), was observed in the composite, which was first hot pressed at 800°C for 1 hour and then annealed for another 8 hours at the same temperature. A detailed EPMA chemical analysis at several selected locations revealed that: (1) at the center of the fiber (I), the observed Al:O ratio was 1.8:3, as compared with the original stoichiometric ratio of 2:3, possibly being resulted from a porous Al₂O₃ phase after a substantial amount of Al ions diffused out to form a new interphase; (2) the reaction layer (II) is shown to have a nominal composition of Bi_{1.52}Pb_{0.25}Sr₂Ca_{1.16}Cu_{0.21}Al_{3.51}O_y, which had substantially lower Cu and Ca contents as compared to those in the matrix (i.e., 2223), due to Al substitution for Cu and Ca ions; and (3) in the matrix 10 μm away from the interface (III), the composition was kept approximately at the original 2:2:2:3 ratio.

Unlike the Al₂O₃/BPSCCO composite, the MgO/BPSCCO interface was relatively inert after an extended heat treatment. In Fig. 10(b), the high-magnification SEM micrograph reveals several detailed features of a (MgO)_w/BPSCCO with $v_w=10\%$. A clear interface between the MgO whisker and the BPSCCO matrix could be immediately identified. No obvious chemical reaction at the whisker-matrix interface was detected. An EPMA microchemical analysis also revealed the inter-diffusion at the whisker/matrix interface was very limited. A very slight decrease in Mg in the whiskers was noted, whereas a slight trace of Mg appeared in the BPSCCO matrix after a long-term annealing. This strongly suggests that no appreciable chemical reaction occurred between the MgO whiskers and the BPSCCO matrix. The good chemical compatibility between the MgO and

BPSCCO also ensured a promising combination of superconducting and mechanical properties of the $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite.

Fig. 10 SEM micrographs showing the interface of (a) a $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite after 1-hour pressing and 8-hour annealing (EPMA microchemical analyses conducted at marked locations I, II, and III.); and (b) a $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite undergone three-cycle hot pressing and annealing.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides important information on processing-structure-property relationships of two HTS composite systems which have been successfully developed in the authors' laboratory, i.e., Al_2O_3 -fiber and MgO -whisker reinforced BPSCCO HTS composites. The HTS composites, especially the $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$, have been demonstrated to possess a combination of desired superconducting and mechanical properties suitable for bulk HTS applications. Based on the current results obtained, the following conclusions may be drawn:

- (1) Processing methods for fabrication of both the Al_2O_3 -fiber and the MgO -whiskers reinforced BPSCCO HTS composites were successfully developed. Proper processing parameters and associated conditions were established for each HTS composite.
- (2) In both HTS composite systems, processing variables, such as hot pressing pressure and time, annealing temperature and time, are critical to control the microstructure, and, consequently, resulting composite properties.
- (3) Owing to the plate-like grains, the BPSCCO matrix was observed to align preferentially in an HTS composite during heat treatment. This preferred alignment significantly enhanced the matrix density and intergrain connections, therefore resulting in improved composite properties.
- (4) No interaction was detected at the $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$ interface, due to their excellent chemical compatibility. On the other hand, a fiber/matrix interfacial reaction was found to occur in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BPSCCO}$ composite after an extended annealing. This interfacial reaction was critical to resulting HTS composite properties.
- (5) Due to excellent thermodynamic and thermomechanical compatibilities, the $(\text{MgO})_w/\text{BPSCCO}$ composites possess desirable, combined superconducting and mechanical properties; and they may be suitable for future HTS bulk applications.

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